

Image of O₂ dynamics released by oak wood submerged in model wine with nanoparticle sensors

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Abstract

Oxidation of wine while in contact with oak wood is a well-known fact and recognized as an important process in wine ageing. The slow and continuous diffusion of oxygen from the oak wood entrapped in its porosity occurs and encourages the reactions usually related with wine aging. In this work, oxygen sensitive particles were used to study the oxygen dynamics from different anatomical regions of the oak wood and simultaneously the oxygen increase because of the deoxygenation of the wood and the oxygen depletion due to its consumption by the tannins and other compounds released from the wood. To this end, core-shell-type PSPVP nanoparticles stained with Macrolex Fluorescence Yellow and Pt-TFPP were employed as reference and oxygen-sensitive particles respectively. Moreover, a Guppy Pro RGB camera was employed to monitor the particles performing ratiometric oxygen imaging, using the green and red channels to acquire the light emitted from the reference and the oxygen-sensitive particles respectively. Because the volume of nanosensors corresponding to each surface unit is very different from that of the wood region, different exposure times were chosen to obtain the images at each of the times. The results show the wood degassing process during the first minutes of the experiment, the oxygen release from different structural elements of the wood, its consumption by the released compounds from wood and the diffusion of the oxygen through the model wine.

Keywords

Optical oxygen sensors; oak wood; oxygen diffusivity; barrel; wood anatomy; wine

1. Introduction

The ageing of wines in barrels improves their quality [1,2], as the wood provides the wine with different components and the barrel allows oxygen to enter from the outside [3], modulating the ageing process; its entry depends directly on how impregnated the wood is [4,5].

The wood structure plays an important role since each area has a different ellagitannin content and

this has high oxygen avidity. Several studies have shown that the increase in the growth ring leads to an increase in the tannic composition of French oak wood [6]. Earlywood has more fibre, more cellulose, and therefore releases more guaiacol and 4-Methyl2,6-diMeOphenol. The concentration of cis-whisky-lactones and eugenol is significantly higher for wine aged in tight-grain barrels with a higher proportion of earlywood [7]. The increase in French oak wood grain implies a decreased oxygen transfer rate [3].

Wood as a porous material has air inside (20.96% O₂) which is released into the wine causing self-oxygenation; this process is different in barrel staves and when using alternatives [8], where the wood is completely submerged in the wine. The measurement of dissolved oxygen with optical sensors based on luminescence has been established in the last decade because they allow non-invasive and contactless monitoring [9]. They are available in various formats such as planar sensor foils and spots, paints, fiber-optic (micro) sensors and nanosensors [10]. In recent years, nanosensors have become an attractive alternative that combine flexibility and robustness. Oxygen sensitive nanoparticles have been applied for intracellular measurements [11–14] in microbioreactors from ml to μ l scale [15–17], microdroplets [18,19] among others [20]. Luminescence lifetime determination and imaging was applied for quantification in various examples. These techniques have superior performance but need specialized and expensive equipment. Alternatively, two-wavelength ratiometric imaging methods have been used [13], which require simpler equipment at lower costs. The different imaging methods were compared by Meier et al. [21] Koren et al. has employed nanosensor particles in combination with ratiometric imaging to visualize oxygen dynamics on coral surfaces and seagrass rhizosphere [22, 23]. In this work we employ nanosensor particles based on Poly(styrene-block-1 vinylpyrrolidone) (PS-PVP) introduced by Borisov et al. [24]. In other reports oxygen nanosensors made from this material were used for lifetime measurements in the frequency domain and imaging in the time-domain [15–17]. Here, we combine oxygen sensitive and reference nanosensors based on this material to perform two-wavelength imaging with a colour camera. We apply a mixture of PS-PVP based nanoparticles stained with an oxygen sensitive dye (Pt-TFPP) and nanoparticles stained with a reference dye (Macrolex Yellow).

The main objective of this work is to use spherical nanosensors combined with an RGB camera to determine both the dynamics of wood degassing and the oxygen consumption of the compounds released by the different anatomical structures of the wood.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of PSPVP nanoparticles for oxygen sensing and referencing

Poly(styrene-block-1-vinylpyrrolidone) particles (PSPVP particles) purchased from Aldrich as a 38% dispersion in water, consisting of 64% w/w of styrene and 36% w/w of vinylpyrrolidone, size < 500 nm, were used for staining. The PSPVP nanoparticle dispersion (1000 mg dispersion

containing 380 mg particles) was diluted with water (50 ml) and THF (30 ml). The mixture was stirred and THF (20 ml) containing Platinum(II)-5,10,15,20-tetrakis-(2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorophenyl)-porphyrin (Pt-TFPP) (3.8 mg) was added dropwise. All THF and parts of water were removed under reduced pressure to a final volume of 38 ml. Therefore, the final particle concentration of the oxygen-sensitive nanoparticle stock was 10 mg ml⁻¹.

For the reference particles PSPVP nanoparticle dispersion (1000 mg dispersion containing 380 mg particles) was diluted with water (50 ml) and THF (30 ml). The mixture was stirred and THF (20 ml) containing Macrolex Yellow (3.8 mg) was added dropwise. All THF and parts of water were removed under reduced pressure to a final volume of 38 ml. Therefore, the final particle concentration of the reference nanoparticle stock was 10 mg ml⁻¹ [24].

PSPVP nanoparticles are water-soluble and can also be dissolved in hydroalcoholic solution. A mixture with 1.25 ml of oxygen-sensitive and 0.625 ml of reference nanoparticles was prepared and dissolved in 25 ml of hydroalcoholic solution to simulate the real situation of the wine aging process. The hydroalcoholic solution was prepared with ethanol (Scharlau, Barcelona, Spain) and water purified in a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) mixed at 13% v/v. This solution was used for both the calibration procedure and the experiments, which will be presented below. The dyes used for staining the nanoparticles do not dissolve in water or ethanol or a mixture thereof. A degradation of the particles in the hydroalcoholic solution was not observed during our investigations.

2.2. Oak wood stave sampling and handling

In this assay, French oak wood (*Quercus Petraea*) from Tonelería Intona S.A., located in Navarre (Spain), was used. The wood was selected for its anatomical structure, as it allows a differentiation of the morphological structures. A piece of wood (0.45×0.47×25.6 mm³) was fixed in the measuring cell with a minimal quantity of acidic silicone, applied in the two small sides of the piece of wood. This wood handling allowed the differentiation between latewood, earlywood and medullary rays, and the visualization of the release of air trapped in the different microstructures of the oak wood.

2.3. Study of the interference of the compounds released by the wood

In order to rule out any possible interference that the compounds produced by the wood could present when illuminated with UV light, they were analysed using the UV/VIS Lambda 25 spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer[®] Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). Performed analysis showed that the emission wavelength of the oak wood chemical compounds was between 280 and 300 nm, so they do not interfere with the nanoparticles emission wavelengths, which are over 500 nm.

2.4. Measurement setup

The measurement setup employed in the experiments performed in this article is shown in Fig. 1. The setup is composed by the measurement cell, an illumination UV LED, a RGB camera, an oxygen probe and a gas mixer: the measurement cell (55×55×20 mm³) was made of Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), whose transparency (92% Transmission) allows the nanoparticles oxygen content image to be captured (Fig. 1); the UV LED consists of a multichip LED array (7×3 W) (Cree, Inc. North Carolina, United States) with a emission wavelength of 405 nm; the camera employed was a Guppy Pro F201C colour camera (Allied Vision Technologies GmbH; Stadtroda, Germany); the oxygen probe consisted of a calibrated O₂ optode system (Oxygen dipping probe TROXROB3 connected to an oxygen metre FirestingGO2; PyroScience GmbH, Aachen, Germany); and the gas mixer was the GM-3 gas mixer of the SensorSense company (SensorSense, The Netherlands). This measurement setup was employed in the calibration of the nanosensors and in the later experiments, and it will be named as calibration setup and experimental setup respectively. This measurement setup was adapted depending on whether it was employed to calibrate the nanosensors or to perform the experiments.

Fig. 1. Configuration of the measuring cell containing the piece of oak wood and a diagram of the different densities of the nanosensors of the wine solution model by measuring surface.

In the calibration procedure, the measurement cell was filled with the model wine with nanosensors solution without including the piece of wood. The oxygen levels of the model wine with sensing particles were modified with the help of dry compressed air and nitrogen, which were mixed using the GM-3 gas mixer. Different oxygen levels were set and measured between 0% and 100% air sat., in 10% steps. Simultaneously the O₂ level in the cell was monitored by means of the calibrated O₂ optode system and images from the measurement cell were acquired. To ensure that equilibrium was reached, each calibration step was held for 60 min. The calibration was obtained by comparing the measured image ratios with the measured O₂ level.

In the experimental procedure, a piece of wood (parallelepiped) was placed into the measurement cell as it can be seen in Fig. 1. This piece of wood was fixed to the measurement cell applying acidic silicon in the two short borders of the wood, ensuring that the region of wood analysed with the camera did not have silicon on it. After fixing the piece of oak wood to the measurement cell, it was filled with the model wine with nanosensors solution with a previously fixed oxygen level, leaving a 1 mm gap between the even surface of the piece of wood and the transparent cell cover. Both the O₂ optode system and the camera were simultaneously initialized and started just before filling the measurement cell with the solution in order to acquire data since the wood starts interacting with the nanoparticles.

2.5. Imaging

The excitation of the sensor particles was done with the UV LED. The LED was powered by a USB-controlled LED driver unit for fluorescence imaging applications and controlled with an Arduino-based system. This system turned on the LED 5 s before each image acquisition in order to have a constant LED intensity during the acquisition procedure and turned off when the acquisition procedure finished in order to reduce any possible nanoparticle stress caused by constant illumination during long periods of time. A long-pass emission filter OG515 (515 nm) from Schott (www.schott.com) together with the Guppy Pro F201C RGB camera were used for image acquisition. The camera uses the Sony ICX 274 CCD 1/1.8 image sensor together with a manual zoom lens, 18–108mm EFL, f/2.5. A program designed with the LabVIEW 2015 platform (and the Vision Development Module; National Instruments, Austin TX, USA) was employed to manage the image acquisition procedure. The camera was configured to obtain images with different exposure times at each acquisition time.

2.6. Image analysis and calibration

Acquired colour images were analysed using a program designed with the LabVIEW 2015 software (and the Vision Development Module; National Instruments, Austin TX, USA). This image analysis program performs two tasks: the calibration procedure and the processing procedure. In both tasks, the red and green channels of the CCD-camera were employed to work with ratiometric imaging: the oxygen sensitive emission of Pt-TFPP was detected in the red channel, while the emission of the reference dye was detected in the green channel. The sensor allowed accurate real-time 2D oxygen imaging with superior quality compared to intensity imaging [25].

The calibration task consisted of adjusting the Stern-Volmer calibration curve to the data extracted from a set of images of the nanoparticle sensors under known oxygen concentrations. A region of interest (ROI) was selected on each image, analysing the red and green channels separately. The mean value of the red channel pixels of the ROI was divided by the mean value of the green channel pixels of the ROI on each RGB image, obtaining a ratiometric value associated to each image. After

that, the Stern-Volmer calibration curve was adjusted to fit the point cloud consisting of the O₂ concentration values versus the inverse of the mean ratiometric values, which were normalized to have a ratiometric mean value of 1 for O₂ = 0% (Fig. 2). Data obtained from oxygen varying from 0% air sat. to 100% air sat. and from 100% air sat. to 0% air sat. was employed to generate the calibration curve in order to take into account the possible hysteresis of the nanoparticle sensor, that is, the difference in sensor measurements when the oxygen concentration was increasing or decreasing.

Fig. 2. Left: False colour images representing the % air sat. obtained from ratiometric images (ratio between the red and green channel extracted from RGB images) of liquid at various defined O₂ levels in wine side chamber. Right: A calibration curve calculated by fitting the Stern-Volmer model ($R^2 > 0.975$) to the R_0/R values vs. O₂ concentration data obtained from the region of interest (ROI) highlighted in (A), where R is the red/green ratio and R_0 is the value of R for O₂=0%. Symbols and error bars represent means ± 5 * standard deviation; $n=5$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

The processing task consisted of transforming the acquired colour images into oxygen images, where the value of each pixel is its oxygen concentration. To this end, the RGB images were transformed into ratiometric images and, after that, the calibration curve previously adjusted was applied to the ratiometric images to obtain the oxygen images.

2.7. Experimental setup

In a second configuration of the measurement setup after the calibration procedure, a piece of

Quercus petraea oak was introduced into the chamber and filled with the hydroalcoholic solution with nanosensors at an oxygen concentration of 0% air sat. A 1mm thick nanosensors layer was created between the oak sample and the transparent cell cover, as it can be seen in Fig. 1. The thickness of the nanosensors layer is constant because both the wood and the cell cover have even surfaces. To speed up the process, the ratio of wood to liquid was 80 times higher than that produced in a barrel. This system was also monitored with the oxygen-dipping probe to confirm the information provided by nanosensors on the concentration of oxygen in solution. Room conditions remained constant throughout the analysis at a temperature of 16 °C and a pressure of 956 hPa.

The control software developed was programmed to capture an image every 5 min and was out of synchronisation with the optical measurement of the immersion probe to avoid light interference. These measurements allowed us to monitor the oxygen obtained from ratiometric images and a measurement sensor that confirmed the measurement. When the dissolved oxygen content of the liquid was to be interpreted, and given that the solution was translucent, the volume of nanosensors corresponding to each surface unit was very different from that of the wood region, where the volume of hydroalcoholic solution was ten times smaller per surface unit. To solve this situation, different exposure times (20 ms, 40 ms, 60 ms and 80 ms) were chosen to obtain the images at each moment.

3. Results and discussion

This study evaluated the possibility of obtaining 2D images of the distribution of O₂ within a fluid containing a piece of oak. A model wine solution was prepared with the nanoparticles of dissolved optical sensors and subsequent ratiometric images were obtained. It should be noted that this method is intended for laboratory investigations as a complement to measurements with other types of sensors already used [26,27], and which allow the fluid to become a sensor. The method was evaluated by studying the dynamics of O₂ released from wood and the consumption of water-soluble compounds released from wood. The method's advantages and limitations are discussed here.

3.1. Global oxygen image generation

The colour signal provided by both the reference and the oxygensensitive nanoparticles depended on the density of nanoparticles present in the region of each pixel of the image. In our experiments, the volumetric density of nanoparticles varied because the depth of the liquid over the wood surface was lower than the depth of the liquid outside the wood surface. For this reason, a single oxygen image cannot be used to analyse the oxygen distribution of the complete experiment region. Analysing the images represented in Fig. 3, many pixels are out of range: approximately 5% of the image with an exposure time of 20 ms and 70% for the image with an exposure time of 80 ms.

Moreover, a significant number of pixels of the red and green images with an exposure time of 20 ms had a low value, which meant that the signal was low, so the signal to noise ratio was also low and therefore the oxygen estimation error would be higher.

Fig. 3. Images taken with two different exposure time values: RGB image with a exposure time of 20 and 80 ms (a); red channel images with a exposure time of 20 and 80 ms (b); green channel images with an exposure time of 20 and 80 ms (c); oxygen image with an exposure time of 20 ms and 80 ms (d). Original oxygen images calculated from images acquired with an exposure time of 20 ms and 80 ms (d), and resultant oxygen image combining the original ones with the proposed procedure (e). Pixels in white represent those whose acquired signal intensity is not valid, that is, red or green pixel values out of range (0 or 255). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

To overcome this problem, a combination of the oxygen images with different exposure times was needed in order to have a valid oxygen distribution image. To this end, the following procedure is proposed to create this image:

$$I_{global}^{ox}(x, y) = \frac{I_a^{ox}(x, y) \cdot f\{I_a^R(x, y)\} \cdot f\{I_a^G(x, y)\} + I_b^{ox}(x, y) \cdot f\{I_b^R(x, y)\} \cdot f\{I_b^G(x, y)\}}{f\{I_a^R(x, y)\} \cdot f\{I_a^G(x, y)\} + f\{I_b^R(x, y)\} \cdot f\{I_b^G(x, y)\}}$$

where, I_{global}^{ox} is the resulting final oxygen image, I_a^{ox} , I_a^R and I_a^G the oxygen, red channel, and green channel images for an exposure time of 20 ms, respectively, I_b^{ox} , I_b^R and I_b^G the oxygen, red channel and green channel images for an exposure time of 80 ms, respectively, and f is a function whose equation is shown below:

$$f(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{max}} & \text{if } \alpha \leq \alpha_{max} \\ \frac{255 - \alpha}{255 - \alpha_{max}} & \text{if } \alpha > \alpha_{max} \end{cases}$$

with α_{max} being the argument where the function f is 1, and having a linearly decreasing value when its argument moves from α_{max} , 0 being the minimum value for the argument values $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 255$. Applying the proposed procedure, the resultant image obtained is presented in Fig. 3e. The calculation for some different pixels is presented in Table 1 in order to show how the proposed equation works.

Table 1.- Example of the application of the equation to combine images with different exposure times for four pixels highlighted in Fig. 3, where R, G and O₂ are the red, green and oxygen values assigned to this pixel for each exposure time considered, O₂ result is the oxygen estimated for the combined image, and weight is the percentage assigned to the oxygen measured for each image in O₂ result.

Region	Exposure time								O ₂ result
	20,045 ms				80,045 ms				
	R	G	O ₂	Weight	R	G	O ₂	Weight	
A	56	52	16	17.74%	246	200	7	82.26%	9
B	0	10	255*	0%	48	40	9	100%	9
C	12	6	0	5.56%	36	34	17	94.44%	16
D	98	86	12	100%	255	255	21*	0%	12

3.2. Wood degassing visualization

Fig. 4 shows the arrangement of the piece of oak wood inside the device and details the areas selected for study on the surface of the wood, differentiating between early and latewood (Fig. 4). The distribution of a layer of model wine with nanosensors on the wood allowed the content of dissolved oxygen released from the wood over time to be known. The images obtained after 0, 10, 30 and 60 min allowed the bubbles generated due to the progressive release of air trapped in the porosity of the wood to be visualized.

Fig. 4. An RGB initial image without 405 nm illumination before adding the model wine, with the ROIs analysed in this article highlighted in white at the top of the figure. The green channel images and the oxygen images after 0, 10, 30 and 60 min are shown in the left and right part of the bottom section of the figure respectively, with the medullar rays highlighted in yellow and the border between the earlywood and latewood highlighted in white. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

The images of the green channel (Fig. 4) show perfectly how air accumulations appeared and quickly grew over time, increasing the size of the initial bubbles. The ratiometric images of O₂ concentration, analysed at an 80 ms exposure time in the wood (Fig. 4), show an evolution over time of the dissolved oxygen content of the model wine. At the beginning of the experiment the concentration of model wine with nanosensors is seen to be equal to the initial concentration of the liquid entering the test, i.e. 0% air sat. This content increased with time due to the release of air from the wood and the progressive dissolution from the surface of the air bubbles released into the liquid. The nanosensors were dissolved in the model wine, which means that there was no signal inside the bubbles. The air-liquid interface of the bubbles and the process of dissolution of the oxygen released by the wood that passes into the model wine, thus enriching it, are shown in both the green channel and the oxygen images. Due to the small separation between wood and glass, a very thin layer of model wine is formed allowing the inside of the bubbles to be visualized, as there is not enough space for the complete bubbles to fit.

3.3. Oxygen distribution along the wood structural parts

The study of the layer of model wine with nanosensors, immediately next to the wood, allowed us to record the oxygen released from each part of the wood as well as the oxygen consumption of the water-soluble compounds released to the model wine by the wood (Fig. 5). Thus, if the average DO value is analysed, after 6.5 h from the beginning of the experiment the dissolved oxygen content of both the liquid on the earlywood and, after 9 h, the liquid on the latewood, can be seen to decrease. This result indicates that from that moment onwards, the dynamics of dissolution of the oxygen released from the air trapped in the wood is less than the dynamics of consumption of that oxygen by the compounds released by the wood. At these times, there is also a greater oxygen release in the latewood area than in the earlywood area, a situation maintained for the first 24 h of the study. This result, which is apparently contradictory, since latewood has a higher density than earlywood, could be explained by the existence of tylosis in the vessels of earlywood, which prevents complete flooding (with the model wine) of the great vessels of earlywood, preventing the consequent displacement of the air they contain. The area of earlywood was later observed to present a slightly higher oxygen content until the end of the experiment (80 h), possibly due to the fact that the latewood yields more ellagitannins eager for oxygen. It is easy to see that dark latewood areas release more oxygen than lighter areas, mainly due to their lower density and therefore higher porosity. In the animation (additional material) this phenomenon can be seen perfectly, as well as the deformation of the wooden piece that has forced us to make a careful monitoring of the regions studied here.

Fig. 5. Oxygen distribution evolution along time, where earlywood and latewood regions are highlighted in order to analyze the differences between these two different structural parts. In the lower part of the figure a graph of the evolution of the mean oxygen content in the earlywood and latewood analyzed regions is shown.

3.4. Oxygen distribution along the model wine

Diffusion of the oxygen released by the wood to the different areas of the model wine with nanosensors is shown in Fig. 6. Each region has a width of 3 mm and a length of 1 mm, EW1, EW2 and EW3 being the regions close to the earlywood and LW1, LW2 and LW3 the regions close to the latewood. The diffusion of the oxygen released from the earlywood area and from the latewood area to the three study regions located within the model wine (Fig. 6) can be seen. Initially, the oxygen released into the liquid was greater than its consumption, with maximum oxygen content from the earlywood reaching around 25–27% air sat. produced after 3.5 h in the region closest to the wood (EW1 zone), after 4 h in the EW2 zone and after 4.5 h in the EW3 zone. Subsequently, until 10 h' study, the oxygen content decreased rapidly to values of 13–17% and from 20 h until the end of the experiment, the tendency was to maintain these levels near 10.6% air sat. in all areas of the liquid studied.

Fig. 6. Oxygen distribution evolution over time, where six regions inside the model wine, placed close to earlywood and latewood regions, are highlighted in order to analyze the differences between these regions. In the lower part of the figure a graph of the evolution of the mean oxygen content in the three earlywood regions (EW1, EW2 and EW3) and latewood regions (LW1, LW2 and LW3) and the differences among them is shown.

With regard to diffusion from the latewood area, oxygen was found to diffuse with a slight delay, since the maximum content was observed after 4 h in the LW1 zone and 6 h in the LW2 and LW3 zones. It is interesting to note that after 6 h continuous decrease, due to the consumption of oxygen by the substances released by the wood, a period began in which the kinetics of release was observed to be higher than the kinetics of oxygen consumption. Thus, an increase in the dissolved oxygen content was observed after 10 h, 13 h and 16 h in zones LW1, LW2 and LW3, respectively, to reach a new maximum oxygen content after 15 h in zone LW1, 19 h in zone LW2 and 24 h in zone LW3. These results can be explained by the possible percolation phenomenon that occurs during the flooding of the wood with the consequent abrupt exit of the gas trapped on it.

The evaluation of the difference in the dissolved oxygen content of the liquid from the earlywood and latewood regions (EW-LW, Fig. 6) shows a phase shift in the 3 regions studied. This phase shift suggests slow diffusion of the oxygen released that has not been consumed, and also shows the increase in the volume of influence of oxygen released, since after 64 h the dissolved oxygen content is almost equal in the 6 regions studied.

4. Conclusion

A method for visualizing the distribution of O₂ concentration and its dynamics over the surface and the immediately surrounding liquid of oak wood pieces submerged in a model wine with O₂ sensitive nanoparticles and subsequent ratiometric imaging with a RGB camera system assembled from commercially available inexpensive components is presented. The use of different exposure times made it possible to visualize the dynamics of oxygen transfer-consumption of a wood submerged in a model wine, in regions close to the wood, as well as in the liquid itself, observing the influence of distance from the wood. Due to this solution, the resulting images presented a high signal level, so the signal to noise ratios were also high and, because of that, the estimation error was lower. Moreover, the resolution of the images made it possible to visualise the differentiated release of O₂ from different anatomical but contiguous regions of the wood. This system is thus postulated as a tool capable of differentiating the behaviour of small areas, something that is difficult to visualise or measure with other systems. This relatively simple methodology and configuration can be applied in many other scientific applications, using the medium involved in the phenomenon, as a sensor capable of monitoring the modifications to which it is subjected.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found, in the online version.

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